

POSITION OF BANKS IN FINANCING INVESTMENT PROJECTS

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In the context of the introduction and development of innovations and information technologies in the banking system, an increase in the capitalization of commercial banks is of great practical importance for strengthening the liquidity and financial stability of banks. It is capitalization that helps to increase the resource potential of a company through additional attraction of direct and portfolio investments. For this reason, the volume of the financial market is very closely related to the level of capitalization. In addition, the higher the capitalization, the higher the collateral value of the company, the more loans it will be able to attract to develop its business. Within the framework of a separate institution, the level of capitalization characterizes the ability of its managers to prove the prospects of the activity of this institution [1].

It should be noted that developed countries have accumulated many years of advanced theoretical, methodological and practical experience in the field of increasing capitalization, modeling, forecasting, analysis, assessment and regulation of the financial stability of commercial banks. The study of advanced foreign experience in this area is of great practical importance for further increasing capitalization, strengthening liquidity and financial stability of commercial banks in Uzbekistan in the context of introducing innovations into the economy [2].

The global development of market relations in the modern economy requires commercial banks to develop and improve methods for strengthening capitalization and financial stability, based on the principles of the market and economic rationality. In particular, in the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, in the section of development and liberalization of the economy, special attention is given to deepening the reform and ensuring the stability of the banking system, the level of capitalization and the deposit base of banks; strengthening their financial stability and reliability; further expansion of lending to promising investment projects [3].

The results of a study of the financial and banking system of developed and developing countries show that the capitalization of commercial banks

directly affects the development and stability of the country's economy [4]. Also, bank loans support the development of small and medium-sized businesses, private entrepreneurship and stimulate the development of infrastructure for an innovative and digital economy in the country [5].

Table 1

Analysis of the main indicators of commercial banks in Uzbekistan (billion soums) [6]

Nu.	Name of indicator	2020	2021	2022	change 2022/2020	
					billion soums	%
1	Actives	214,420	272,727	366,121	151,701	70,7
2	Credits	167,391	211,581	276,975	109,584	65,5
3	Capital	26,679	51,031	58,351	31,672	118,7
4	Deposits	70,001	91,009	114,747	44,746	63,9

As can be seen from Table 1, commercial banks have high growth rates for all asset indicators. Thus, in relation to 2019, in 2021, the assets of commercial banks increased by 70.7 percent, the loan portfolio by 65.5%, capital by 118.7% and deposits by 63.9% [7].

Figure 1. Loan portfolio by types of clients [8]

Illiquid assets include: overdue loans, fixed assets and property of the bank.

In the course of quantitative analysis, the composition and structure of the bank's loan portfolio is studied in dynamics (for a number of years, for quarterly dates of the reporting year) according to a certain number of quantitative economic criteria and characteristics, which include: the volume and structure of loan investments by type; the structure of credit investments by groups of borrowers (loans to legal entities, loans to individuals); terms of loans; timeliness of repayment of provided loans (presence of overdue loans); industry affiliation; types of currencies; the price of lending (the level of interest rates). Such an analysis makes it possible to identify priority areas of lending, trends in the development and repayment of loans and their profitability. The scope of the borrower's activity and its type carry different risks for certain economic conditions. In this regard, the types of loans, depending on the volume and purpose of lending, are evaluated and characterized in different ways, which should be taken into account when studying the bank's loan portfolio. For this, different relative indicators are used, which are calculated by turnover for a certain period or by the balance on a certain date [9]. These indicators include the share of problem loans in the entire gross client loan portfolio or the ratio of overdue debt to equity and others.

In recent years, international banking practice has seen fundamental changes in the activities of commercial banks. The further development of digital technologies in the economy and, in particular, the banking system is due to global progress in the fields of information technology and telecommunications [10].

Later, the concept of asset and liability management of the bank emerged. Different authors have paid different attention to this issue. So, in the fourth edition of "Banking" under the editorship of the foreign scientist economist Kolesnikov V.I. there is the concept of asset and liability management, but only as part of the liquidity management process: "The bank's liquidity management process includes a set of actions and methods for managing assets and liabilities" [11].

The main activities of the bank are lending to the real sector of the economy of Uzbekistan, financing projects for technical and technological modernization in order to promote the production of competitive products and create new jobs. A

special place in the work of the bank is occupied by financial support for small businesses and private entrepreneurship [12].

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